

Research Article

Analysis of clinical characteristics of 18 children with vasovagal syncope(VVS)

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Abstract: Objective to explore the clinical features of children with vasovagal syncope (VVS) and improve their understanding of the disease. Methods The clinical characteristics of 18 patients diagnosed with VVS in the First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University through an Head-up tilt test(HUTT) were retrospectively analyzed and the differences in gender, number of syncope attacks, posture at the time of attack, duration and performance of syncope aura were compared.

Result: A total of 18 cases were selected, aged 7-16 (10.8 ± 2.5) years old, 9 males and 9 females, the ratio of men and women was equal, the number of syncope attacks was 1-3 times, the most common was the first attack and the duration of syncope was 1-30 Minutes, mostly within 5 minutes. The postures of syncope are upright, sitting, squatting and not positioning, the symptoms of syncope are various. Conclusion VVS patients are more common in older children, without gender differences, the clinical characteristics are quite different and the prognosis is good.

Keywords : Vasovagal syncope, syncope, VVS, head up tilt test, HUTT, syncope in children.

Introduction

Syncope is a transient loss of consciousness caused by transient global cerebral hypoperfusion and symptoms of unsustainable posture [1]. The occurrence of syncope in childhood and adolescence is common, vasovagal syncope (VVS) is the most common [2]. In recent years, China has carried out a series of studies on the basic of clinical aspects of vasovagal syncope in children and has achieved valuable research results which greatly improved the diagnosis and treatment of syncope in children [3-5]. This study retrospectively analyzed the clinical characteristics of 18 children who were hospitalized in the First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University and were diagnosed as VVS by the head up tilt test. This study aim to improve the pediatricians understanding and diagnosis of this disease.

1 Data and methods

1.1 Research subjects

A total of 18 cases with vasovagal syncope were diagnosed in the First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University pediatric inpatient ward from January 2019 to June 2019. Ages are 7 to 16 (10.8 ± 2.5) years old, 9 males and 9 females. After detailed examination of medical history, physical examination, conventional electrocardiogram(ECG), chest X-ray, echocardiogram, blood biochemistry (myocardial enzymes, fasting blood glucose), electroencephalogram(EEG) and head magnetic resonance image (MRI) to exclude the diseases of circulatory system, central nervous system, respiratory system and other organic diseases. Completed Head up tilt test(HUTT) with the consent of child and his family.

1.2 Inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria:

Inclusion criteria: ① Detailed medical history records, including syncope and syncope aura symptoms, syncope inducement, etc .; ② Clearly record the (HUTT) Head up tilt test and positive test when diagnosing VVS.

Exclusion criteria: ①Incomplete data and incomplete medical history; ②Those who did not take HUTT at the time of diagnosis; ③After examination, it was determined that syncope was caused by organic heart disease or other diseases.

1.3 Data collection

Collect basic data of all cases, including gender, age, presence or absence of triggers, syncope aura, duration of syncope, number of episodes and accompanying symptoms. Then organize and analyze the data. The diagnostic criteria of VVS through HUTT and HUTT procedure method is done as per the criteria of 2016 revised version of the diagnostic guideline for syncope in children[3].

1.4 Statistical method

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 26.0 statistical software. The measurement data conforming to the normal distribution is expressed by the mean value $\pm$ standard deviation, the measurement data of the deviation distribution is expressed by M (Q) and the count data is expressed by n (%). Taking $\alpha = 0.05$ as the test level, $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

2. Results

2.1 A total of 18 cases were selected, aged 7 to 16 (10.8 ± 2.5) years old, 9 males and 9 females, the

ratio of male and female is equal. Height (138.4 ± 11.7) cm, weight (32.1 ± 8.8) kg.

2.2 The number of syncope episodes at the time of admission was 1.5 ± 0.6 times (1-3 times), the first onset accounted for 61.1% (11/18) and the second onset accounted for 27.8% (5/18), the third Only 11.1% (2/18) visited the clinic after the attack.

2.3 Postures during syncope are standing (33.3%, 6/18), sitting (27.8%, 5/18), squatting (22.2%, 2/18), and indefinite position (27.8%, 5/18).

2.4 The duration of syncope is 1-30 minutes, of which one minute is the most common, accounting for 44.4% (8/18), 77.8% (14/18) within 3 minutes and 94.4% (17/18) within 5 minutes.

2.5 The symptoms of syncope are varied, among which the symptom of chest tightness and palpitations being the most common, accounting for 50% (9/18), followed by paleness and sweating, accounting for 27.8% (5/18) and abdominal discomfort accounting for 27.8% (5/18), dizziness and blurred vision accounted for 16.7% (3/18) and there were no other symptoms of syncope accounted for 22.2% (2/18).

Discussion

Syncope is one of the common emergencies in childhood and 60% –70% of them belong to VVS. Most of the first attacks of VVS are in childhood and adolescence [6]. A 15 year retrospective analysis of the etiology and clinical characteristics of autonomic nervous mediated syncope in children and adolescents has been carried out in a single center in China. A total of 3182 cases were included, 1649 cases were male, 1533 cases were female, 2-18 years old, average age (10.7 ± 3.1) years old [7], suggesting that vasovagal syncope is more common in older children and studies on vasovagal syncope in older children are also carried out in china as well as different countries [8-11]. The 18 children included in this study were 7 to 16 years old with an average of (10.8 ± 2.5) years old, consistent with previous studies.

The pathogenesis of VVS is not completely clear. Factors such as autonomic dysfunction, increased levels of catecholamines and decreased venous return may be involved in the occurrence of the disease [12]. In a study by Login et al. [9] to understand the changes in sympathetic nerve activity in children with vasovagal syncope through heart rate variability analysis, the children were divided into groups of 5 to 11 years and 12 to 15 years according to age. The size and sympathetic nerve activity of the two groups of patients are stronger than the healthy control group. The posture of children with syncope is more common in the standing position and the incentives are posture change, permanent standing, mental stress and hot and humid environment [3]. The 18 cases of vasovagal syncope children included in this study were mainly the initial onset of illness and the

posture of the attack was not definite, which may be related to the cases in which all the cases included in this study were hospitalized with syncope. Some cases of syncope which are mainly caused by repeated attacks outside hospitals, the outpatient doctors in our hospital have been diagnosed with necessary examination such as detailed medical history, physical examination, electrocardiogram and other necessary examinations. Most cases in hospital are atypical outbreak, which need to be further excluded from patient with cardiopulmonary disease.

VVS patients lose consciousness for more than 5 minutes, can be identified with cardiac syncope and epilepsy [3]. In this study, the majority of children with syncope duration is within 5 minutes (94.4%), especially within 1 minute (44.4%). Therefore, for those who can't spontaneously resolve for long period of syncope, we also need to consider other organic lesion other than vasovagal syncope. Tian Juan et al [7] found that the clinical symptoms in VVS were unexplained syncope, dizziness, chest distress, chest pain, headache, etc. This study found that common symptoms of syncope include chest distress, palpitations, paleness, sweating, abdominal discomfort, dizziness, blurred vision, etc. Therefore, clinically it is often necessary to distinguish from atypical asthma, hypoglycemia attacks and other diseases. Some children may have no obvious symptoms of syncope. After the diagnosis of vasovagal syncope is clarified, health education is carried out to the children with the syncope, so that the children can be timely deal when the syncope occurs, thus reducing the occurrence of syncope and accident injury.

Most vasovagal syncopes have a rapid onset, a short duration, and a good prognosis. Obtaining accurate information and detailed physical examinations during syncope attacks is the basis for diagnosing the disease. HUTT is an important test for diagnosis. After the diagnosis is clear, it is necessary to give the related information of syncope needs to parent and children, health education to parents and children in a timely manner, avoid triggers, identify the precursors of syncope and carry out physical anti-stress actions, proper physical exercise and autonomic nerve function exercises which can make most children's syncope effectively controlled. The 18 cases in this study were observed after being discharged from hospital with a follow up observation that the average number of episodes was reduced or not repeated. Drug therapy may be considered for those who have repeated episodes, have insignificant signs of attack, have a risk of trauma or have poor curative effect with non-pharmacological treatment. For those who have recurrent syncope accompanied by prolonged cardiac arrest (> 4 s) and CPR survivors, consider installing a pacemaker [13-15].

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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